

Momentum Viewpoint of Quantum Bound State

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In a previous note (1), we argued that $\exp(ipx)$ is the mathematical form of a probability type function which ensures momentum conservation. In other words, we argued that quantum mechanics (at least the $\exp(ipx)$ part), is due to finding a probability function which conserves momentum. Given a momentum p , one associates it with a particle moving with momentum p , but if one only knows momentum, one does not know its rest mass or velocity. We found that the probability function is $\exp(ipx)$ with \hbar/p defining a physical wavelength, an idea which is more general than what is contained in Newtonian mechanics.

We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ should not be thought of in terms of a classical trajectory. It is a probability which when multiplied by $\exp(-ipx)$ and integrated over dx shows whether there is momentum conservation or not. As a result of using probabilities linked to momenta, one may mix completely different classical times (as in a classical particle moving forwards and backwards) in a bound state. In classical physics, momentum conservation occurs at a point, but the general $\exp(ipx)$ form indicates that one requires a length of at least \hbar/p . If \hbar/p is very small compared to the system length, then one essentially has classical physics. Otherwise, a more general physics applies, namely quantum mechanics.

For a bound state, we argue that momentum conservation in interactions of a particle with a potential are key, yet overall energy must be conserved at each x as well. We suggest that if p is the key variable, then there should be a probability $P(p)$. This means that the bound state may be thought of in terms of a set of allowable p 's, their $\exp(ipx)$ s, their weights $a(p)$ such that $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ and operator expectation values.

Operator expectation values follow from the generalization of $\int dx W^* W$ to $\int dx W^* \text{operator } W$. In other words, one sees if Operator W may transition, in keeping with conservation of momentum, to W^* .

. One does not think in terms of classical hits at a specific x point and following a particle in time. One describes the problem in terms of p 's and $\exp(ipx)$ s which indicate that a certain p may be present and that it must conserve momentum if it interacts (and one integrates over all x). Conservation of momentum does not appear at a single x due to the wavelength.

If a bound state is really thought of in terms of different momentum states, which are orthogonal (momentum conservation) over space, then each state has a kinetic energy (unnormalized) of $pp/2m a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and $W^* (-i\hbar/dx)(-i\hbar/dx) W$ yields the sum: $\sum_p a(p)^* a(p) pp/2m$. Similarly, the overall energy E is associated with $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities and $E \int W^* W dx = E \sum_p a(p)^* a(p)$. Physically, however, $V(x)$ should render impulse hits to the particles changing one p to another. Again, one does not follow the particle in time and does not think of a hit at a particular x value. One may consider, in keeping with momentum conservation: $\int dx W^* V(x) W$. Only interactions which conserve momentum survive this integral. This shows a coupling of different momenta due to $V(x)$. If one writes $V(x)= \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$, then $\exp(ikx) \exp(ipx)$ simply means that a momentum p can become $p+k$. One is not interested at which point in space this occurs because one is only interested in momentum and its conservation. The integral $\int dx W^* V(x)W$, however, shows various combinations which may combine with $a^*(p)\exp(-ipx)$ from W^* so one has a coupled $V(x)$ with all a_p 's which links to

$\exp(-ipx)$, namely $\sum_k a_k \exp(ipx)$. Thus, one thinks of a set of p 's with $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities to ensure conservation of momentum, but $V(x)$ allows one to create a p value from a k (of $V(x)$) and a p_1 from the set of p 's. The overall result, however, is the creation of a p from the set of p 's which describe the bound state because one focuses on momentum and its conservation.

Classical Mechanics versus Momentum Probability

Classical mechanics follows a particle in x,t and one observes an interaction in a tiny dx which changes velocity. We have argued in (1), that one may start with the fundamental idea of conservation of momentum and create a probability math function which ensures conservation of momentum, namely:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

In order to see conservation of momentum, one needs the complex conjugate of a second $\exp(ip_1x)$ and one must integrate over at least a portion of x . As p and p_1 become large, i.e. \hbar/p becomes very small with respect to the system length, one only has to integrate over a small x region and one has classical physics.

Thus: $\int W^*(x)W(x) dx$ or $\int W^*(x) \text{operator } W(x) dx$ becomes a key operation with $W(x)=\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Here one sums over the possible p values in the system regardless of the time in which they may be created. One is not following a particle in time, one is only writing the set of p 's which may appear, together with their $\exp(ipx)$ s which ensure momentum conservation.

Thus, classically a particle moves to the right for some time and then to the left in a different time interval in a bound state. This is completely physical and still applies to quantum mechanics. The $\exp(ipx)$ probability prescription, however, does not follow the particle in time. If the particle may have a p and later a $-p$, one writes $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and $a(-p) \exp(-ipx)$ and ignores the different times. This is a probability view. One collects the allowable probabilities and their $\exp(ipx)$ for momentum conservation.

Bound State

If one decides to describe a bound state in terms of momenta and $\exp(ipx)$ s, then one is suggesting that momentum conserving interactions occur. One does not assume that elastic collisions occur. One wishes to describe the system in terms of the allowable momenta, their weights $a(p)$ and momentum conserving probability functions $\exp(ipx)$ as well as operator expectation values. In the above section, we noted that the integral $\int dx W^*W$ is key to show allowable momentum conserving transitions, but one may also consider $\int dx W^* \text{operator } W$ and this shows momentum conserving interactions between W^* and Operator W . Thus, for a bound state, we consider the operators:

$$\frac{1}{2m} \hbar^2 (-i\hbar/dx) (-i\hbar/dx) \text{ for kinetic energy} \quad ((2a))$$

$V(x)$ ((2b)) for potential energy and

E ((2c)) for constant overall energy.

Then: ((2a)) yields for $\int dx W^* \text{Operator } W = \sum_p a(p)^* a(p) p^2/2m$. ((3a))

((2c)) yields $E \sum_p a^*(p)a(p)$ ((3c))

We interpret ((3c)) in the following way. The bound state is described solely in terms of the p that are allowable and their probabilities $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$. Thus, $\sum P(p)=1 = \sum_p a^*(p)a(p)$.

Given that E is the total energy, and each p has a probability $P(p)$, one might say that a p is responsible for $P(p) E$ of the energy.

The key term in terms of momentum conservation is $\int W^* V(x) W$ ((2b)). This yields:

$\sum_p a^*(p) \{ \sum_k V_k a(p-k) \}$ ((3b))

Thus, momentum conservation means that hits to p_1 (taken from the p set describing the bound state) can receive a k hit from $V(x)$ and create the momentum p . The $\exp(ipx)$ approach is to consider momentum conservation and to include all possible forms which create momentum p . Thus, ((3a)) and ((3b)) combine to create ((3c)) on a $p, \exp(ipx)$ basis.

We suggest that formalism of the bound quantum system is one of probabilistically describing the state in terms of the allowable moment, their weights and associated operator expectation value pieces. It is not a dynamic picture of following a particle in time and space.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that classical physics involves following a particle in x,t and watching it interact in a little dx which tends to 0. We suggest that quantum mechanics is based on the math probability $\exp(ipx)$ which ensures momentum conservation through: $\int dx \exp(-ip_1x) \text{operator } \exp(ip_1x)$. This may be generalized to: $\int dx \exp(-ip_1x) \text{operator } \exp(ip_1x)$ to find transitions from Operator $\exp(ipx)$ to $\exp(-ip_1x)$ which conserve momentum. We note that \hbar/p , the wavelength in $\exp(ipx)$ is a physical feature. For classical physics, \hbar/p is very small compared to the system length.

As a result, a bound state in the momentum conservation probability scheme is simply described in terms of allows p 's (all p values), their weights $a(p)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ s and one computes: $\int W^* \text{operator } W dx$, where $W = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, to see which transitions (momentum impulse hits) conserve momentum.

For a bound state, this leads to: $\int dx W^* (1/2m \hbar^2) (-id/dx)(-id/dx) W$, $\int W^* V(x)W dx$ and $E \int W^*W dx$.

One finds that $V(x)$, written as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$, allows for transitions from $k+p_1$ to p which conserve momentum. Thus, the system is still describe in terms of p values and their associated energies (as the operator), but $V(x)W(x)$ creates p terms from various k from $V(x)$ and p_1 's from the allowable p set, i.e. there is a coupling, but overall the system is described in terms of p values (linked to $\exp(ipx)$) and associated energies, $a^*(p)a(p)p^2/2m$ or coupled pieces, $a(p) \sum_k V_k a(p-k)$, but both are associated with momentum p . The point we make is that the momentum probability scheme is one of listing allowable momenta, their weights and associated operator expectation values,.It is a tallying kind of approach.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Conservation of Momentum in terms of Probability, Space and Time (preprint, zenodo, 2024)